

Economic Analysis of Catfish Farming in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria

Fave. B. Filli

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Godiya Bulus

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Federal University Wukari, Taraba State, Nigeria

Helen B. Inyang

Department of Agricultural Economics and Extension, Faculty of Agricultural Sciences National Open University of Nigeria, Kaduna State, Nigeria

Suggested Citation

Filli, F.B., Bulus, G. & Inyang, H.B. (2023). Economic Analysis of Catfish Farming in Makurdi Local Government Area, Benue State, Nigeria. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(4), 1213-1222.
DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(4\).111](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(4).111)

Abstract:

This study assessed the economics of catfish farming in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. Snowball sampling techniques was used in selecting 84 catfish famers for the study. Data was collected through the use of structured questionnaire, administered to the selected catfish famers. Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics, net farm income and multiple regression analysis. Costs and return structure showed a mean value cost of production ₦1, 151, 460.67 with mean revenue of ₦1, 788, 663 and a gross margin of ₦703, 776.33. Gross ratio and operating ratio were 1.55 and 0.61, respectively; while, return per naira invested was 61k.

The greater than one value of gross ratio indicated that catfish farming was profitable; while a less than one operating ratio shows that catfish farmers were efficient in managing costs. The result of the regression showed that fingerlings have a positive and statistically significant at 1%, feed at 5% and the f-value is significant at 1%. The coefficient of multiple determinant R^2 was 0.899. Nevertheless, excessive production costs and improper use of inputs were found to have affected the profitability of medium and small-scale fish farmers. Most of these farmers have low years of experience (below 10 years) accounting for about 52.38% of the total respondents. It is concluded that fish farming was profitable in the study area. Therefore, it is recommended that fish farmers in the study area need to acquire more training on the business management aspect of fish production.

Keywords: *Economic, Analysis, Catfish, Farming, Markurdi.*

Introduction

Fish is an important source of animal protein for many households in Nigeria and in many other countries of the world. According to FAO (2018), fish contribute more than 60% of the world supply of protein, especially in the developing countries. Traditionally fish is

harvested in their natural habitats which are water bodies. Over time man come to understand that fish found in such places become less sufficient in supply due to depletion and drying up of such environments. Artificial means of producing them through intensive management, therefore, becomes an

indispensable alternative. The process of fish production described as extensive is a situation whereby fish are cultured or raised in an environment similar to their natural habitat (Irou et al., 2019).

Nigeria is endowed with a huge potential for fish farming. As a maritime nation with a vast population of over 200 million people and a coastline measuring approximately 853 kilometres, fish production as an enterprise possesses the capacity to contribute significantly to the agricultural sector (Osagie, 2012). Fish farming as an economic activity was first introduced into Nigeria about 66 years ago with the establishment of a small experimental station at Onikan in Lagos State, Agodi in Ibadan, Oyo State, and an industrial farm (20 hectares) at Panyam in Plateau State by the Federal Government of Nigeria (Ayodele and Ajani, 1995). With an annual fish demand in the country of about 2.66 million tonnes, and a paltry domestic production of about 780,000 tonnes, the demand-supply gap stands at a staggering 1.8 million tonnes. Despite the popularity of fish farming in Nigeria, the fish farming industry can best be described as being at the infant stage when compared to the large market potential for its production and marketing (Nwiro, 2012). A right step towards arresting the demand-supply deficit for fish is aquaculture, which involves raising fish under controlled environment where their feeding, growth, reproduction and health can be closely monitored (Ejiola and Yinka, 2012). Aquaculture practices as a business venture is capable of bringing significant development in the rural and urban areas by improving family income, providing employment opportunities and reducing problems of food supply and security (Akinrotimi et al, 2009).

In order to bridge the demand-supply gap, an aquaculture transformation agenda plans to increase annual fish production from the current production of 0.78 million MT to 3.0 million tonnes in order to achieve self-sufficiency in fish production and supply by the year 2015 (Tijani, 2011). This will be achieved through fish farm development program, fish seeds and feed mill development program, fish pen and cage culture

development program and fish post-harvest management and marketing program of information on the integral role of the fishery sub-sector to the nation's economy, there exists a dearth of empirical information on the linkage between fishery production and economic growth in Nigeria and its perspective for sustainable economic development which ought to form the basis for policy formulation towards enhancing the fishery sub-sector. Given the aforementioned, there is the need to fill the existing gap in literature by providing empirical information on the nature of causal relationship between fishery production and economic growth of those involved in the business. In view of the foregoing, this study was carried out to achieve the objectives describe the socioeconomic characteristics of fish famers, identify the activities involved in cat fish farming, estimate the profitability of fish, determine factors influencing the catfish production and identify the constraints associated with fish farming in the study area.

Methodology

Study area

This study was conducted in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. The Local Government Area is located on latitude $7^{\circ}44'$ and $7^{\circ}55'$ North of the Greenwich Meridian Time and longitude $8^{\circ}20'$ and $8^{\circ}40'$ East of the equator. It is located on the bank of Benue River and it experiences warm temperature due to the valley of the river Benue. The major markets are the North-bank market, modern market and Wurukum market. The river Benue which passes through parts of the Local Government is a source of water for irrigation which makes dry season farming possible in the area, most of the people farm vegetables at the river bank where the source of water is close. The river is also a good source of water for fishing. The rising population of the area and the increased demand for fish protein provide favourable environment for fish farming to meet the increasing demand for fish.

Figure1. Map of Makurdi Local Government Area
Source: Research gate (2020)

Sampling Techniques

A multi-stage sampling technique was employed in selecting cat fish farmers for this study. First stage was the purposeful selection of Makurdi town based on the concentration of cat fish farmers. Second was the snowball selection of 84 cat fish farmers.

Method of data collection

Data for this study was derived mainly from primary source which was collected with the use of structured questionnaires administered to 84 cat fish farmers in the study area using snowball techniques. The information gathered through the use of questionnaires included socioeconomic characteristics of the cat fish farmers (age, sex, level of education, household size, farming experience, source of capital), the inputs used (fingerlings, feed, water, fertilizer, lime, drug, labour), the output of the farming exercise (the quantity of table size fish harvested in kilogram) as well as expenditure of fish farmers on food and non-food items and

problems militating against cat fish farming business.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics was used to analyze the socio-economic characteristics of the respondents, describe food security status, identify the causes and coping strategies of food insecurity, while food security index and multiple regression model was used to determine food security status of households and factors influencing food security, respectively.

Net Farm Income Analysis

Net farm income analysis was used to determine how profitable fish farming business is in the study area. It will be used to achieve objective iii. The net farm income specifically provides the amount of money that has been returned to the owner of the farm or business for their investment of labor, management and other resources. This analytical technique was used to estimate the profit or the net income which is the difference between the gross farm income and

the total costs of production (Olukosi and Erhabor, 1988). The model is specified as follows:

The net farm income model is specified as follows:

$$NFI = TR - TC \quad (1)$$

Where;

NFI = Net Farm Income,

TR = Total Revenue and TC = Total Cost (Total Variable Cost + Total Fixed Cost).

Profitability ratios such as operating ratio (OR), gross ratio (GR) and rate of return on naira invested (RNI) were computed as follows:

$$OR = \frac{\text{Total variable cost}}{\text{Total Revenue}} \quad (2)$$

Operating ratio shows the efficiency of a farm's management by comparing the total operating expense of a farm to net sales. An operating ratio of less than 1 therefore indicate that the farmer is efficient in managing costs while an operating ratio of 1 or greater than 1 indicates inefficiency in costs management.

$$GR = \frac{\text{Total Revenue}}{\text{Total Cost}} \quad (3)$$

Gross ratio shows the profitability or otherwise of a farm by comparing its total revenue to total costs. Higher ratio, of greater than 1, indicates profitability of the enterprise while lower ratio, of less than 1 shows that the enterprise is not profitable.

$$RNI = \frac{\text{Gross Margin}}{\text{Total Variable Cost}} \times \frac{100}{1} \quad (4)$$

Return per naira invested gives a measure of the profitability of a farm firm by expressing its gross margin as a percentage of the total variable cost. The percentage is then used to indicate the magnitude of the return per each naira invested in the business.

Multiple Regression Model

Multiple regression models were used to determine the factors influencing fish output in the study area. Four functional forms were used and double log was adopted as the best fit for the analysis.

The model is specified as follows:

The empirical model that will be used in the study is specified as:

$$\ln Y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln X_1 + \beta_2 \ln X_2 + \beta_3 \ln X_3 + \beta_4 \ln X_4 + \beta_5 \ln X_5 + \beta_6 \ln X_6 + \beta_7 \ln X_7 + u_i \dots (5)$$

Where;

Y = Total fish output in kilogram per production period

X₁ = size of the pond in meter cube (m) (earth or concrete)

X₂ = number of fingerlings

X₃ = labor (man-days)

X₄ = quantity of feed (kg)

X₅ = value of drugs used (₦)

X₆ = quantity of water supplied (liters)

X₇ = fuel used (liters)

u_i = error term

Results and Discussion

Socio-Economic Characteristics of Respondents

Socioeconomic characteristics of the catfish farmers were considered in this section of the study to identify those characteristics that may explain catfish farming activities in the in the study area. They include age, sex, marital status,

household size, educational level, farming experience, source of capital, income and pond location. Age is very important in agricultural production as it determines the physical strength of the individual, and young people tend to withstand stress, put more time in various agricultural operations which can result to increased output. The results presented in Table 1 shows that the farmers' age ranged from 20 to 70 years. Majority (80%) of the catfish farmers fall within the age of 30 -50 years. The mean value of age indicated that the average age of the farmers was 40 years. This means that the farmers are within active productive age bracket that could easily adopt to new techniques for production. The results from table 1 revealed that the majority (75%) of the catfish farmers are male, while 25% were female. This implies that fish farming in the study area is dominated by male gender. This is in agreement with the findings of Mohammed et al., (2015) and Ume et al; (2013) in which they found that majority of catfish farmers in Lagos and Anambra States respectively were male. Marital status revealed that majority of the respondents (69%) in the study area were married, where 31% were not married. This implies that fish farming is an enterprise undertaken by married people and this may be that they see it as a means of livelihood for income generation for the family. In addition, married people are seen to be responsible according to societal standards. Family members are also a source of labour on the farms. Greater family size would mean that the cost of paid labour provided by hired labour would be less. The result presented in Table 1 shows that majority (56%) of the respondents have a family size of less than or equal to 5 persons while 31% of them have a household size of 6 – 10 persons. The average household size of the respondents was 5. Therefore, the farmers would be forced to hire labour and pay for hired labour as they are enlightened enough to send their wards to school. This shows that a lot of hired labour will be needed to supplement the insufficient family labour they have which will result in increased cost of production. The educational level of farmers also plays an important role in agricultural production. Findings of the study in Table 1 showed that

96% of the farmers had one form of formal education or the other while only 4% had no form of formal education. This result could also be attributed to the urban nature of the study area as the farmers that engaged in catfish production have acquired some form of formal education. It is of general opinion that experienced farmers would be more efficient, have a better knowledge of climatic conditions and market situations and are thus expected to run a more efficient and profitable enterprise. The result revealed that catfish farmers had less than or equal to 5 to greater than 10 years of experience. Most of the farmers (52%) had less than or equal to 5 years of experience in catfish farming, followed by 25% respondents who had 6-10 years of farming experience. This indicates that catfish production is relatively a new enterprise and most people were just in the process of learning the art of catfish production.

Table 1. Socioeconomic Characteristics of Respondents

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
21-30	12	14.29
31- 40	20	23.81
41 – 50	31	36.90
51- 60	16	19.05
61-70	5	5.95
Total	84	100
Sex		
Male	63	75
Female	21	25
Total	84	100
Marital status		
Single	19	22.62
Married	58	69.05
Widow /widower	4	4.76
Divorced	3	3.57
Total	84	100
Household size		
1-5	23	27.38
5-10	47	55.95
11-15	11	13.09
16-20	3	3.57
Total	84	100
Farming Experience		
1-5	39	46.43
5-10	21	25.0

11-15	19	22.62
16-20	5	5.95
Total	84	100
Educational Level		
Non	3	3.57
Primary	16	19.5
Secondary	33	39.29
Tertiary	32	38.09
Total	84	100

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Activities Involved in Fish Farming in the Study Area

Table 2 presents the various activities carried out in fish farming in the study area. The activities considered in this study included record of production period, fingerlings production, mortality rate, feeding frequency per day, type of feed and source of labour. The table revealed that majority (42%) of the respondents had a production period of 26-30 weeks followed by 37% who had production period of 31-35 weeks. The mean production period of the farmers was 28 weeks. This means fish production in the study area takes 6-7 months to reach a table size. The result on the table revealed that majority (93%) of the respondents' purchase the fingerlings for their farms while only 7% produced fingerlings themselves. This implies that there is low production of fingerlings in the study area. Record on mortality rate revealed that 92% of the respondents had a mortality rate of equal to or less than 5% while 8% recorded mortality of greater than 5%. This could mean that the weather water quality of the study area is conducive for fish farming. On feeding activities of the respondents, it was revealed that majority (87%) feed their fish twice a day, while 7% and 6% of the respondents feed their fish once and more two times respectively. From the table it was revealed that most (89%) of the farmers feed their fish with pelletized feed, while 11% of the respondents used compound feed. This means that majority of the farmers in the study area can afford pelletizer they use to make their feed. The record from the table revealed that majority (77%) of the respondents depend on family members for their source of labour, while 8% of the respondent's use hired labour

for their farming activities. This could be because most of the farmers have their farm located within their residence; hence any available person can serve on the farm.

Table 2. Pond Activities

Activities	Frequency	Percentage	Mean
Production period			28.35
20-25 weeks	12	14.29	
26-30 weeks	35	41.67	
31-35 weeks	31	36.90	
36-40 weeks	6	7.14	
Total	84	100	
Fingerlings Source			
Self-production	6	7.14	
Purchase	78	92.86	
Total	84	100	
Mortality rate (%)			2.54
0-5	77	91.67	
6-10	7	8.33	
Total	84	100	
Feeding per day			
1	6	6.14	
2	73	86.90	
3	5	5.95	
Total	84	100	
Feed type			
Pelletized	75	89.29	
Compound	9	10.71	
Total	84	100	
Source of labour			
Family	65	77.38	
Hired	7	8.33	
Mixed	12	14.29	
Total	84	100	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Profitability of Fish Farming in the Study Area

The aim of every business is to maximize profit through optimum production. In agriculture, increasing yield with minimal cost on input gives optimum production, where profit is maximized. Profitability analysis of every business gives the

solvency of the business. It also, advices on where to improve business and minimize unnecessary expenses (wastage) are involved. Table 3 presents Net Income Analysis accruable to fish farmers in Makurdi, Benue State. The table revealed that the average variable cost (AVC) of the respondents was N1, 084,886.67 while the average fixed cost (AFC) was ₦66, 574.00 per production cycle. The feeds constitute about 71.27% of the variable cost on fish production which is quite high as compared to other inputs used. Therefore, the total cost (ATC) of fish production by the respondents was ₦1, 151,460.67 per production cycle. Also, the total revenue (TR) from the output was ₦1, 788,663.00 per production cycle with a gross

margin (GM) N703, 776.33. Net farm income (NFI) of the respondents was N637, 202.33. Return per every naira invested was 61%, implying that for every ₦1 invested 61 kobo was realized. This therefore, established that fish farming was profitable in Makurdi, Benue State. Thus, agreeing with the work of Kudi et al., (2008); Emokaro et al., (2010) and Filli, (2011) who reported positive profit margins associated with fish farming. An operating ratio of 0.61 indicated that farmers were efficient in managing resources, while a gross ratio of 1.55 indicated that the farmers realized a return above the cost of production. However, the business is capital intensive especially the running cost that needs proper planning and implementation.

Table 3. Average Cost and Return on Fish Farming per Production Cycle of Six Months

Variable	Value (₦)	Percentage (%)
A. Total Revenue	1, 788, 663.00	100
B. Variable Costs		
i. Fingerlings	154,333.00	14.23
ii. Feeds	773,187.00	71.27
iii. Water	91,897.00	8.47
iv. Labour	19,173.00	1.77
v. Fuel	15,467.00	1.43
vi. Medication	7,113.00	0.55
viii. Others	23,716.67	0.66
C. Total Variable cost	1,084,886.67	100.00
D. Fixed Costs		
i. Depreciation on capital items	35,107.00	52.73
ii. Pond	31,467.00	47.27
E. Total Fixed Cost	66,574.00	100.00
F. Total Cost of Production (C + E)	1,151,460.67	
G. Gross Margin (A – C)	703, 776.33	
H. Net Farm Income (G – E)	637, 202.33	
I. Operating Ratio (C/A)	0.61	
J. Gross Ratio (A/F)	1.55	
K. Return per Naira Invested (G/F*100)	61%	

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Factors Influencing the Catfish Production in the Study Area

The regression estimates the factors influencing catfish farming are presented in Table 4. From the table, coefficient of multiple determinations (R^2) was 0.899 which implies that about 89.9% of the variation in output of fish (Y) is explained by variables X_1 - X_7 included in the model while the remaining 10.1% is as a result of non-

inclusion of some important explanatory variables as well as errors in the estimation. The F-ratio (167.656) is statistically significant at 1%, this implies that the explanatory variables adequately explained the model. Out of the 7 variables included in the model, only 6 namely fingerlings, labour, feeds, medication, water and fuel were statistically significant at explaining the output of fish. Fingerlings have an estimated

regression coefficient of 0.347 which is positive and statistically significant at 1%. This implies that fingerlings have a positive and statistically 32 significant relationships with return on catfish. This suggests that the more fingerlings stocked the more the output and the more returns will be realized on fish farming in the study area. The co-efficient with respect to labour is 0.166 which is positive and statistically significant at 5% level. It implies that there is a positive statistical significant relationship between labour cost and output. As more money is spent to labour on catfish farming, more returns are realized. Feed was positive and significant at 5% level of significance with coefficient of 0.222. This implies that fish output increases by 0.222 unit as the feeds supply increase by one bag. Results from the table revealed a positive relationship between cost of water and output and number of fish farmers can keep. The coefficient of water is positive and significant at 5%. The size of the pond will determine the quantity of water needed and the number of fingerlings stocked

and consequently, the amount of profit made. The coefficient of medication was 0.154 which positive and significant at 5% level of significance. The positive relationship of medication cost indicates that an increase in cost of medication purchased will result to an increase in total cost of production. It showed that a unit increase in the cost of medication will result to an increase in total cost of production by 0.154. This implies that as more medical care is given to the fish the more the output to be realized. Quantity of fuel had an estimated coefficient of 0.939 with a positive sign showing direct effect on cost of catfish farming. The positive relationship of fuel indicates that an increase in cost of fuel purchased will result to an increase in total cost of production. It shows that a unit increase in the cost of fuel will result to an increase in total cost of production by 0.939%. This result was found to be significant at 1% level of probability. This could be attributed to the low use of fuel by catfish farmers to pump water for the farm.

Table 4. Multiple Regression Analysis

Variable	Unstandardized Coeff.		Standardized Coeff.	t-value
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
Constant	-0.307	6.014		-0.051
Pond Size	-1.189	1.291	-0.155	-0.921
Fingerlings	3.309	1.019	0.347	3.249***
Labour	1.522	0.676	0.166	2.252**
Feeds	1.861	1.412	0.222	1.318**
Medication	1.296	0.661	0.154	1.960**
Water	0.313	0.167	0.050	1.872*
Fuel	7.094	0.201	0.939	35.221***
F-Value				167.656***
R-Square (R ²)				0.899 (89.9%)

Note: ***Significant at 1% level, **Significant at 5% level, *Significant at 10% level

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Constraints Associated with Fish Farming in the Study Area

Various constraints are faced by catfish farmers in the area which results in inability of the farmers to meet the demand for fish are presented in Table 5. The result showed that the major problems encountered in catfish production in the area were inadequate market

outlet (96.4%), High cost of feeds (94.0%), and inadequate capital supply (86.9%). Inadequate market might have pose a challenge to the catfish farmers due to the naira redesigned policy which perhaps limited the potential buyers access to cash. High cost of feeds may have been as a result of the costs ingredients used in compounding the feeds. The combine effect of

these problems on the farming system could bring about a distortion in the structure, conduct and performance of the farming process. Hence,

lead to the reduction in output of the fish farmers.

Table 5. Classification of Respondents Based on Constraints

Constraint	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Ranking
Inadequate capital	73	86.9	3 rd
Insufficient fingerlings	54	64.3	4 th
Inadequate extension service	24	28.7	12 th
Inadequate market outlet	81	96.4	1 st
High cost of feeds	79	94.0	2 nd
High cost of borehole	47	56.0	7 th
Poaching	34	40.5	10 th
Diseases and pests	26	31.0	11 th
High cost of transportation	51	60.7	5 th
Power supply	38	45.2	8 th
Disparity in fish growth	48	57.1	6 th
Labour	35	41.7	9 th

Source: Field Survey, 2023

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, this study shows that catfish farming was profitable in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State. Nevertheless, excessive production costs and improper use of inputs were found to have affected the profitability of medium and small-scale fish farmers. Most of these farmers have low years of experience (below 10 years) accounting for about 52.38% of the total respondents. It is of general opinion that experienced farmers would be more efficient, have a better knowledge of climatic conditions and market situations and are thus expected to run a more efficient and profitable enterprise 36

Based on the findings of the study, it is recommended that;

- Since fish farming is a profitable enterprise, youths should be enlightened and encouraged to invest in it.
- Researches should be carried out to reduce the level of disparity in fish sizes so as to ensure that fishes with similar sizes and weight can be produced.
- Fish farmers should be trained on how to formulate fish feeds so as to reduce cost and increase their profit.

- Extension officers should be trained more on the economic dimension of fish farming and not only the technical aspects which will be delivered to fish farmers to enable them understand the economic aspect of their farm thereby leading to efficient use of resources/farm inputs.

References

- Akinrotimi, O.A., Abu, O.M.G. Ibemere, I.F. & Opara C.A. (2009). Economic viability and marketing strategies of Periwinkle *Tympanotus Fuscatus* in Rivers State Nigeria. *International Journal of Tropical Agriculture and Food Systems*, 3(3), 238-244
- Ayodele, I. A. & Ajani, E. K. (1995). *Essentials of fish farming (Aquaculture)*. Ibadan: Odua Co. Ltd.
- Ejiola, M.T, & Yinka, O.F. (2012). Comparative Cost Structure and Yield Performance Anzlysis of Upland and and Mangroove Fish Farms in Southwest, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agricultural Management and Development*, 2(3), 187-198
- Emokaro, C.O., Ekunwe, P.A. & Achille A. (2010). Profitability and viability of Catfish

Farming in Kogi State, Nigeria. *Research Journal of Agriculture and Biological Sciences*, 6(3), 215-219

FAO. (2018) State of world fisheries and aquaculture. 2018 Food and Agriculture Organization, Rome. FAO, Rome. Retrieved from

<https://www.fao.org/3/I9540EN/i9540en.pdf>

Iruo, F. A., Onyeneke, R. U., Eze, C. C., Uwadoka, C., and Igberi, C. O. (2019). Economics of smallholder fish farming to poverty alleviation in the niger delta region of Nigeria. *Turkish Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 313-329. http://doi.org/10.4194/1303-2712-v19_4_06

Filli, F. (2011). *Homestead Aquaculture in Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria: Socio-economics, Profitability, Technical Efficiency, Allocation Efficiency, Stochastic, Disparity, Constraints*. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing

Kudi, T. M., Bako, F. P., & Atala, T. K. (2008). Economics of Fish Production in Kaduna State Nigeria. *ARPJ Journal of Agricultural and Biological Science*, 17-21.

Mohammed, U.S., Iyiola A.S and Usman, R.K. (2015). Production Analysis of Catfish Farming In Epe Local Government Area of Lagos State, Nigeria. *Production Agriculture and Technology*

Journal Publication of Nasarawa State University, Keffi, 11(2), 153-161.

Nwiro E. (2012). Fish Farming a Lucrative Business. Retrieved from <http://www.thisdaylive.com/articles/fish-farming-a-lucrative-business/119253>

Olukosi, J.O. & Erhabor, P.O. (1988). *Introduction to Farm Management Economics: Principles and Applications*, Agitab Publishers, Zaria, Nigeria.

Tijani, B. (2011). *Federal Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development Action Plan towards the Attainment of a Sustainable Agricultural Transformation in Nigeria*. Being a Lead Paper Delivered at the World Food Day Seminar, Agricultural Show Ground Keffi Road, Abuja, Nigeria. Pp 1-10

Ume, S. I., Onuh, N. C., Jiwuba, F. O., & Onunka, B. N. (2016). Technical Efficiency among Women Cassava Small Holder Farmers in Ivo Local Government Area of Ebonyi State. *Asian Journal of Agricultural Extension, Economics & Sociology*, 12(2), 1-6. <https://doi.org/10.9734/AJAEES/2016/17832>